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List of Abbreviations

COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	European Commission Framework Programme Horizon 2020
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
RI	Research Infrastructure
RTD	Research and Technological Development
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
TA	Trans-national Access
UK	United Kingdom
USA	United States of America
USP	User Selection Panel
VA	Virtual Access

Executive Summary

Following the way paved by its predecessor ERIGrid, the main goal of the ERIGrid 2.0 project is to provide on-site and remote lab access to an integrated Research Infrastructure, operated at 21 distributed installations in 11 countries. The ERIGrid 2.0 lab access programme is offered mainly to the European research community where the need of investigating and validating complex smart grid configurations and smart energy systems is essential.

This document summarises the Laboratory Access or short “Lab Access” (i.e., “Trans-national Access”) activity performed in ERIGrid 2.0 from October 2020, when the 1st call for lab access proposals was launched, until September 2022. The report compiles the different calls, proposals received, and their evaluation by the User Selection Panel. Based on this information, an analysis of the degree of accomplishment of the access provision at partner and project levels is carried out, showing good progress to reach the demanding access objectives of the project.

ERIGrid 2.0 also offers the possibility of Virtual Access to researchers around the world; 10 databases, real-time data or simulation platforms are made available online free of charge. This report compiles and evaluates available statistics and metrics on the usage of these online services until September 2022.

1 Introduction

ERIGrid 2.0 is a pan-European Research Infrastructure (RI), which integrates 21 first-class laboratories located in 11 European countries, and aims at placing this RI at the disposal of the European research community (and also of the international one, with some limitations), including industrial organisations. The project offers a four-year access programme supported by the European Commission (EC) through the European Commission Framework Programme Horizon 2020 (H2020).

ERIGrid 2.0 offers to all interested researchers in the domains of smart grids and energy systems free of charge access to its laboratories and associated services along with logistical, technological and scientific support for their own experimental research.

At the same time, ERIGrid 2.0 provides to researchers worldwide the opportunity to access 10 virtual facilities (databases, real-time data or simulation platforms) free of charge, through the so-called Virtual Access (VA) modality.

This document compiles and summarises the lab access (i.e., Trans-national Access (TA)) and VA provision during the first 2.5 years of the access programme in ERIGrid 2.0.

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

The objective of this deliverable is to report on the lab access and VA activities performed in ERIGrid 2.0 from its beginning in April 2020 until September 2022. The procedures and conditions of the access schemes in ERIGrid 2.0 have been formulated in Deliverable D6.1 (*D-NA5.1 Specification of the Trans-national Access and Virtual Access Programmes*, 2021) linked to Call 1 for lab access and the launching of the VA services.

This report describes from the administrative point of view the different calls, the proposals received, their evaluation by the User Selection Panel (USP), and their final status regarding lab implementation; based on this information, the document presents the degree of accomplishment of the lab access provision at individual RI and project levels, jointly with several metrics and statistics on the use of the VA on-line services.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: After an executive summary, an introduction on the purpose, scope and structure of the report is provided; the core of the document includes six sections: Section 2 summarises the call timeline and deadlines, Section 3 compiles the proposal received in the different calls for lab access and the current implementation status in the lab, Section 4 details the evaluation process results of the received proposals performed by the USP, Section 5 mentions the user workshops to be organised during the projects lifetime, and finally Section 6 and Section 7 assess the current provision of lab access and VA, respectively. The report ends with the relevant conclusions in Section 8 and an Appendix containing an example of the proposal review report.

2 Laboratory Access Process

As described in Deliverable D6.1 (*D-NA5.1 Specification of the Trans-national Access and Virtual Access Programmes, 2021*), the general call timeline is shown in Figure 1. As a reference, the duration of the call and the associated user access will last for around 12 months, with the following main time periods:

- The call will remain open for 3 months.
- The received proposals will be evaluated by an independent USP within 1 month (2 months maximum) after the closing date of each call.
- The access period must be allocated within 6 months after acceptance of the proposal with a typical duration of 1-4 weeks (and limited to a maximum of 3 months if well justified). The implementation can be split into 2 phases (2 access periods) in the lab, if necessary, but not more.
- After finishing the lab access, there is a two-month time limit for the user group to carry out the mandatory reporting of the project experiments.

Figure 1: Lab access call reference timeline.

In ERIGrid 2.0, lab access calls have been launched every 4 months, with the same reference timeline as outlined in Figure 1. The call sequence for the first three calls is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Sequence of lab access calls.

The reference deadlines of the above steps in the access process have turned out to be really challenging (based on the accumulated experience up to now). Some flexibility had to be provided by ERIGrid 2.0 for the sake of maximising the access provision, especially considering the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic restrictions (including lockdown periods and restricted lab services) of recent years.

When the access is completed at the RIs, the user groups (except Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs)) must prepare a Technical Report of the implemented project. This mandatory document contains the first scientific output on the experiment implementation and results generated by the users, who took advantage of the ERIGrid 2.0 lab access opportunity.

Reports have been received already from the users for 22 completed projects, the remaining reports of the accomplished projects are in progress. All documents are kept in the project internal repository and uploaded to the project's website¹ and Zenodo's ERIGrid 2.0 Community² for public availability.

3.1 1st Call for Lab Access Proposals (05/10/2020 – 31/12/2020)

This section compiles the proposals received in the 1st Call for lab access proposals launched from 5th October 2020 to 31st December 2020. For each proposal, the title, user organisation/s, host infrastructure/s, and access status are presented.

The following list provides an executive summary of the call outcomes:

- 11 proposals received, 9 accepted, 1 withdrawn by user.
- Type of organisation: 8 from Universities + 3 from Industry (SME, and other profit private organisations).
- Expected access duration: 1-5 weeks; 3.1 weeks (average).
- User Groups from:
 - European Union (EU): 3 proposals (Spain, Italy, Denmark).
 - Associated Countries: 3 proposals (Serbia, Turkey, Switzerland).
 - Non-EU: 5 proposals (United Kingdom (UK), United States of America (USA), India, Pakistan).

1	PMU-FFR	<i>Validation of PMU based Fast Frequency Response Control Scheme in P-HIL Environment</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	University of Belgrade	Serbia
		Host Research Installation:	Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory (UST)	
		Access Status:	Under negotiation	---
2	DEFINIT 2.0	<i>DEcentralized Fault IdeNtification for distribution grids using a limited number of measurements of LV voltage and current: development and performance assessment</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Depsys	Switzerland
		Host Research Installation:	Power Networks Demonstration Centre (UST)	
		Access Status:	Completed	5 access days

¹<https://erigrd2.eu/user-projects>

²<https://zenodo.org/communities/erigrd2>

3	COLOUR-POWER	<i>Wavelet-Transform based Signal Processing for the Validation of Power Flow Tracing Approach</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	University of Glasgow	UK
		Host Research Installation:	Distributed Energy Resources Test Facility (RSE)	
		Access Status:	Completed	10 access days
4	AutonoM	<i>Autonomous Microgrid Controller</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Middle East Technical University	Turkey
		Host Research Installation:	SYSLAB and Energy Systems Simulation Lab (DTU)	
		Access Status:	Completed	10 access days
5	POLARIS	<i>POwer sharing for Low-inertia Assets in Renewable-based Inverter Systems</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Virginia Tech	USA
		Host Research Installation:	Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory (UST)	
		Access Status:	Completed	15 access days
6	SES-MGES	<i>Stochastic Multi-objective Scheduling of Smart Energy System considering Multi-generation Energy Storage</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Aalborg University	Denmark
		Host Research Installation:	SESA-Lab (OFFIS)	
		Access Status:	Completed	27 access days
7	Hytechnet	<i>Multi-criteria evaluation of hydrogen technologies for the design of distribution networks based on renewable energy</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	H2Cloud Energy	Spain
		Host Research Installation:	Electrical Sustainable Power Lab (TU Delft)	
		Access Status:	Withdrawn by user	---
8	M-ECHall	<i>Renewable Energy Community "Energy City Hall" of the City of Magliano Alpi (Italy)</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Energy City Hall	Italy
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Grid Interoperability Lab in Ispra, IT (JRC, EC)	
		Access Status:	Completed	9 access days
9	BAMLEV	<i>Electric Vehicle Battery Degradation Analysis and Estimation using Machine Learning Techniques</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Lahore University of Management Sciences (LUMS)	Pakistan
		Host Research Installation:	---	
		Access Status:	Not approved	---
10	RT-SimVal	<i>Real-time simulation and validation of integrated Fault classification and Section Identification (IFCS) Method in Distribution Network (with and without DG integration) for faster service restoration using real-time measurements and state estimation of CFPIs</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	University of Petroleum and Energy Studies (UPES)	India
		Host Research Installation:	Electrical Sustainable Power Lab (TU Delft)	
		Access Status:	Under negotiation	---

11	OEM-MGR	<i>Optimal Energy Management of Micro Grids with V2G and Renewables</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Lahore University of Management Sciences (LUMS)	Pakistan
		Host Research Installation:	---	
		Access Status:	Not approved	---

3.2 2nd Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/02/2021 – 30/04/2021)

This section compiles the proposals received in the 2nd Call for lab access proposals launched from 1st February 2021 to 30th April 2021. For each proposal, the title, user organisation/s, host infrastructure/s, and access status are presented.

The following list provides an executive summary of the call outcomes:

- 13 proposals received, 11 accepted, 1 withdrawn by user.
- Type of organisation: 11 from Universities + 2 from Research Institutions.
- Expected access duration: 2-5 weeks; 3.6 weeks (average).
- User Groups from:
 - EU: 8 proposals (Finland, Austria, Malta/Cyprus, France, Germany, Poland).
 - Associated Countries: 1 proposal (Norway).
 - Non-EU: 4 proposals (Russia, India, UK).

1	DPSSEC	<i>Distributed power system state estimation and cybersecurity in smart grid</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Skolkovo institute of science and technology	Russia
		Host Research Installation:	---	
		Access Status:	Not approved	---

2	PROOF	<i>Adaptive protection for microgrids based on communication</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Lappeenranta University of Technology (LUT)	Finland
		Host Research Installation:	Electric Energy Systems Laboratory (ICCS-NTUA)	
		Access Status:	Completed	18 access days

3	VOIDIP	<i>Enabling LVRT-HVRT functions and Power Curtailment in Microgrid using Disturbance Identification and Islanding Information with Micro PMU</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur	India
		Host Research Installation:	Electrical Sustainable Power Lab (TU Delft)	
		Access Status:	Under negotiation	---

4	DeMaDsVal	Data Driven Detection of Malfunctioning Devices in Power Distribution Systems Validation		
		User Group Organisations:	Austrian Institute of Technology	Austria
		Host Research Installation:	Power Networks Demonstration Centre (UST)	
		Access Status:	Completed	19 access days
5	GRIDPV100	Innovative RES Solutions for 100% RES Systems (GRIDPV100)		
		User Group Organisations:	Malta College of Arts, Science and Technology FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy	Malta Cyprus
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Electricity Systems and Technologies Laboratory (AIT)	
		Access Status:	Completed	30 access days
6	DynOMO	Dynamic Interaction of Offshore Wind Farm Through MTDC Network with Onshore AC Grid		
		User Group Organisations:	Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur	India
		Host Research Installation:	---	
		Access Status:	Not approved	---
7	SIM HES-OFF	Simulation Platform for Hybrid Energy Systems in Offshore Oil & Gas Installations		
		User Group Organisations:	NTNU – Dept. Electric Power Engineering (IEL)	Norway
		Host Research Installation:	Real-Time Lab (RWTH Aachen University)	
		Access Status:	Completed	20 access days
8	PPIF	Primary Support in Finland		
		User Group Organisations:	Grenoble INP	France
		Host Research Installation:	Intelligent Energy Testbed (VTT)	
		Access Status:	Completed	17 access days
9	Open-CAN-Verter	Study of the expansion of microgrids using software defined power converters and open CAN-based communication architecture		
		User Group Organisations:	LAAS CNRS	France
		Host Research Installation:	Electric Energy Systems Laboratory (ICCS-NTUA)	
		Access Status:	Completed	10 access days
10	VaFlexPot	Validation of a flexibility potential model and network use cases		
		User Group Organisations:	TU Dortmund University	Germany
		Host Research Installation:	SYSLAB and Energy Systems Simulation Lab (DTU)	
		Access Status:	Completed	9 access days
11	CREAM	Cascade Reduction with an Epidemic Analysis Method		
		User Group Organisations:	University of Sussex	UK
		Host Research Installation:	Real-Time Lab (RWTH Aachen University)	
		Access Status:	Withdrawn by user	---

12	PViPS	<i>Photovoltaics Integration in Distributed Power Systems</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	AGH University of Science and Technology	Poland
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Electricity Systems and Technologies Laboratory (AIT) Flex Power Grid Laboratory (KEMA Labs) Low Voltage Experimental Microgrid Lab (FOSS-UCY)	
		Access Status:	Completed	25 access days

13	resIMG	<i>Resilience-oriented Microgrid Control and Protection</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Hochschule Darmstadt University of Applied Sciences	Germany
		Host Research Installation:	Electric Energy Systems Laboratory (ICCS-NTUA)	
		Access Status:	Completed	8 access days

3.3 3rd Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/06/2021 – 31/08/2021)

This section compiles the proposals received in the 3rd Call for lab access proposals launched from 1st June 2021 to 31st August 2021. For each proposal, the title, user organisation/s, host infrastructure/s, and access status are presented.

The following list provides an executive summary of the call outcomes:

- 3 proposals received, 3 accepted.
- Type of organisation: 2 from Universities + 1 from Research Institutions.
- Expected access duration: 4 weeks; 4 weeks (average).
- User Groups from:
 - EU: 1 proposal (Germany).
 - Associated Countries: 1 proposal (Switzerland).
 - Non-EU: 1 proposal (India).

1	PETER	<i>Risk management for electromagnetic interference of smart grid systems, H2020 PETER project</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Bundeswehr	Germany
		Host Research Installation:	National Smart Grid Laboratory (SINTEF)	
		Access Status:	Completed	34 access days

2	FLEVOEWIM	<i>A fuzzy logic based efficient and robust control of EVs with open-end winding induction motor drive</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	National Institute of Technology Warangal	India
		Host Research Installation:	National Smart Grid Laboratory (SINTEF)	
		Access Status:	Completed	20 access days

3	VEHICLE	Validation of benchmark system for charging control investigation		
		User Group Organisations:	Zurich University of Applied Science Ricerca Sistema Energético (RSE) Canmrt ENERGY, Natural Resources Canada (NRCan) University of Strathclyde	Switzerland Italy Canada UK
		Host Research Installation:	SYSLAB and Energy Systems Simulation Lab (DTU)	
		Access Status:	Completed	12 access days

3.4 4th Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/10/2021 – 31/12/2021)

This section compiles the proposals received in the 4th Call for lab access proposals launched from 1st October 2021 to 31st December 2021. For each proposal, the title, user organisation/s, host infrastructure/s and access status are presented.

The following list provides an executive summary of the call outcomes:

- 16 proposals received, 11 accepted, 1 withdrawn by user.
- Type of organisation: 2 from Industry (SMEs) + 12 from Universities + 2 from other organisations.
- Expected access duration: 1-8 weeks; 4.1 weeks (average).
- User Groups from:
 - EU: 4 proposals (Cyprus/Austria, Italy, Czech Republic).
 - Associated Countries: 2 proposals (Turkey, Switzerland).
 - Non-EU: 10 proposals (Chile, India, South Africa, Brazil, Pakistan).

1	PMUs- Cloud	Method for rotational inertia metering and forecasting using cloud synchrophasors data		
		User Group Organisations:	Splight Artificial Energy	Chile
		Host Research Installation:	Electrical Sustainable Power Lab (TU Delft)	
		Access Status:	Withdrawn by user	---

2	VOLTME- TER	Voltage Regulation Monitoring in Distribution Network Integrated with PV and degraded Battery		
		User Group Organisations:	Motilal Nehru National Institute of Technology Allahabad	India
		Host Research Installation:	---	
		Access Status:	Not approved	---

3	DynOMO	Dynamic Interaction of Offshore Wind Farm Through MTDC Network with Onshore AC Grid		
		User Group Organisations:	IIT Kanpur Ostfold University College	India Norway
		Host Research Installation:	Electrical Sustainable Power Lab (TU Delft)	
		Access Status:	Under negotiation	---
4	AIDGRIDS	Artificial Intelligent Digitalized Solutions for Smart Grids		
		User Group Organisations:	University of Cyprus - FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT)	Cyprus Austria
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Electricity Systems and Technologies Laboratory (AIT) Low Voltage Experimental Microgrid Lab (FOSS-UCY)	
		Access Status:	Completed	20 access days
5	CybTEST	Cyber attack in PV system for voltage regulation in distribution network		
		User Group Organisations:	Motilal Nehru National Institute of Technology Alahabad Ostfold University College	India Norway
		Host Research Installation:	Intelligent Energy Testbed (VTT)	
		Access Status:	Completed	20 access days
6	LD-RTCosim	Locally Distributed Real-time Co-simulation Infrastructure for Scalable System Simulation		
		User Group Organisations:	Politecnico di Torino	Italy
		Host Research Installation:	Real-Time Lab (RWTH Aachen University)	
		Access Status:	Completed	40 access days
7	SMPS	Smart Microgrid Protection System		
		User Group Organisations:	IIT Guwahati	India
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Electricity Systems and Technologies Laboratory (AIT)	
		Access Status:	Completed	22 access days
8	AGIPDem	Advanced GPT Inverter Physical Demonstration		
		User Group Organisations:	University of Cape Town	South Africa
		Host Research Installation:	Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory (UST) Power Networks Demonstration Centre (UST)	
		Access Status:	Under negotiation	---
9	HCEQIS	Hosting Capacity and Energy Quality in Isolated Systems		
		User Group Organisations:	eAmazônia – Energia Sustentável e Inovação	Brazil
		Host Research Installation:	---	
		Access Status:	Not approved	---
10	RCPIso	Radio communication as a perpetuity tool for isolated photovoltaic systems		
		User Group Organisations:	CEPEL – Centro de Pesquisas de Energia Elétrica	Brazil
		Host Research Installation:	---	
		Access Status:	Unfeasible	---

11	IoRE	<i>Internet of Renewable Energy (IoRE): Application of IoT/IoE Intelligent Information and Communication System for Purely Renewable Island and Bulk Electricity Networks</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	University of Pardubice	Czech Republic
		Host Research Installation:	---	
		Access Status:	Not approved	---
12	IC2PSofMG	<i>Intelligent Control to Enhance Power Smoothing of DERs based Microgrid</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Dicle University	Turkey
		Host Research Installation:	Distributed Generation Laboratory (CRES)	
		Access Status:	Completed	15 access days
13	SEFL EMTR	<i>Single-end fault locator based on the electromagnetic time reversal theory</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Streamer Electric AG	Switzerland
		Host Research Installation:	Power Networks Demonstration Centre (UST) Demonstration & Experimentation Unit (OCT)	
		Access Status:	Under negotiation	---
14	TRMDRO	<i>Torque Ripple Minimization for DTC of PMSM Drive Using Duty Ratio Optimization</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	National Institute of Technology Warangal	India
		Host Research Installation:	---	
		Access Status:	Unfeasible	---
15	CYPRESS	<i>Cyber-Physical Resilient Distribution System</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Lahore University of Management Sciences	Pakistan
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Electricity Systems and Technologies Laboratory (AIT)	
		Access Status:	Completed	34 access days
16	RE-LENDER	<i>Reinforcement Learning and Nonlinear MPC algorithm for the Distributed Energy Resources</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Politecnico di Milano	Italy
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Grid Interoperability Lab in Petten, NL (JRC, EC)	
		Access Status:	Under negotiation	---

3.5 5th Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/02/2022 – 30/04/2022)

This section compiles the proposals received in the 5th Call for lab access proposals launched from 1st February 2022 to 30th April 2022. For each proposal, the title, user organisation/s, host infrastructure/s, and access status are presented.

The following list provides an executive summary of the call outcomes:

- 11 proposals received, 11 accepted.
- Type of organisation: 1 from Industry (SME) + 9 from Universities + 1 from other organisations.
- Expected access duration: 2-6 weeks; 3.6 weeks (average).

- User Groups from:
 - EU: 3 proposals (France, Spain, Greece).
 - Associated Countries: 3 proposals (Turkey, Norway, Serbia).
 - Non-EU: 5 proposals (Brazil, Iran, India, Egypt, Jordan).

1	Grid Ex-panDER	<i>A cost-effective solution for the non-firm grid connection of Low Voltage Generators</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Roseau Technologies	France
		Host Research Installation:	Test Center for Smart Grids and Electromobility (IEE)	
		Access Status:	Under negotiation	---
2	CPHILT-GFVSC	<i>Control and Power Hardware-in-the-Loop Testing of Grid-Forming Voltage Source Converters</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Universidad de Sevilla	Spain
		Host Research Installation:	Electric Energy Systems Laboratory (ICCS-NTUA)	
		Access Status:	Completed	27 access days
3	PHIL-Rep	<i>Ensuring Replicability of Power HIL Simulations: A Proposal towards a Standards Tests</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	CEPEL	Brazil
		Host Research Installation:	Electrical Sustainable Power Lab (TU Delft)	
		Access Status:	Completed	20 access days
4	EMS4GCHS	<i>Energy Management System for Grid Connected PV-Battery-Diesel Hybrid System</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Dicle University University of Kurdistan	Turkey Iran
		Host Research Installation:	SESA-Lab (OFFIS)	
		Access Status:	Under negotiation	---
5	HIHREMS	<i>Hybridized Intelligent Home Renewable Energy Management System</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Dicle University University of Belgrade	Turkey Serbia
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Grid Interoperability Lab in Ispra, IT (JRC, EC)	
		Access Status:	Under negotiation	---
6	ProMiSe	<i>Assessing the Provision of a Multi-Ancillary Service Framework provided by PV-BES Systems</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Democritus University of Thrace Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	Greece
		Host Research Installation:	Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory (UST)	
		Access Status:	Completed	10 access days
7	PERFECT	<i>PERformance Analysis of PV Integrated Distribution Network with combination of DiffERent Control Strategies and Communication NeTwork</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Motilal Nehru National Institute of Technology Alahabad Ostfold University College	India Norway
		Host Research Installation:	Intelligent Energy Testbed (VTT)	
		Access Status:	Completed	20 access days

8	CyDER-FORT	<i>Fortified Cyber Defense in DER Management Systems</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Marmara University Middle East Technical University	Turkey
		Host Research Installation:	Smart Grid Technologies Lab (TECNALIA)	
		Access Status:	Under negotiation	---
9	IETGPSC	<i>Investigating the Effect of Third Generation Photovoltaics (Large Scale Perovskite Solar Cells) Penetration in Electric Grid</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Kafrelsheikh University-Faculty of Engineering	Egypt
		Host Research Installation:	Electric Energy Systems Laboratory (ICCS-NTUA)	
		Access Status:	Completed	10 access days
10	DynaPEM	<i>Dynamic Characterization of Power-Electronics-based-Microgrid</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Tafila Technical University	Jordan
		Host Research Installation:	Intelligent Energy Testbed (VTT)	
		Access Status:	Completed	8 access days
11	Multigrid-con	<i>Grid Interconnection protocols for Largely Dispersed minigrids/microgrids</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Indian Institute of Technology Bhubaneswar	India
		Host Research Installation:	National Smart Grid Laboratory (SINTEF)	
		Access Status:	Completed	13 access days

3.6 6th Call for Lab Access Proposals (01/06/2022 – 31/08/2022)

This section compiles the proposals received in the 6th Call for lab access proposals launched from 1st June 2022 to 31st August 2022. For each proposal, the title, user organisation/s, host infrastructure/s, and access status are presented.

The following list provides an executive summary of the call outcomes:

- 6 proposals received, 5 accepted.
- Type of organisation: 2 from Industry (SMEs) + 4 from Universities.
- Expected access duration: 1-13 weeks; 4.5 weeks (average).
- User Groups from:
 - EU: 2 proposals (Portugal, Germany).
 - Non-EU: 4 proposals (India, Japan, Iran, Pakistan).

1	TRMDRO	<i>Torque Ripple Minimization for DTC of PMSM Drive Using Duty Ratio Optimization</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	National Institute of Technology, Warangal	India
		Host Research Installation:	---	
		Access Status:	Under negotiation	---
2	ISAIPS	<i>Study of innovative impedance-based stability analysis for the power systems composed of inverter-based resources</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Toyo University	Japan
		Host Research Installation:	National Smart Grid Laboratory (SINTEF)	
		Access Status:	Completed	10 access days
3	FaultTS	<i>Fault TroubleShooter</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	ENEIDA.IO	Portugal
		Host Research Installation:	Power Networks Demonstration Centre (UST)	
		Access Status:	Completed	5 access days
4	Sono LV-MCU	<i>Testing and Validation of LV MPPT Center Unit (MCU)</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Sono Motors GmbH	Germany
		Host Research Installation:	---	
		Access Status:	Under negotiation	---
5	CTCPM	<i>Cyber Threats in Cyber-Physical Microgrids</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	University of Kurdistan Queen Mary University of London	Iran UK
		Host Research Installation:	Intelligent Energy Testbed (VTT)	
		Access Status:	Under negotiation	---
6	CYPRESS-Wood	<i>Cyber-Physical Resilient Distribution System with secondary controller design</i>		
		User Group Organisations:	Lahore University of Management Sciences	Pakistan
		Host Research Installation:	Electric Energy Systems Laboratory (ICCS-NTUA)	
		Access Status:	Under negotiation	---

4 Proposal Evaluation and User Selection Panel

4.1 Lab Access User Proposal Evaluation

The evaluation of the user project proposals in ERIGrid 2.0 is done through two processes running in parallel: (1) pre-screening by the ERIGrid 2.0 laboratories, and (2) evaluation by the USP. The entire evaluation process was expected to be completed within 1-1.5 months after the deadline for the submission of proposals.

The pre-screening is the first assessment of the technical, economic, and organisational feasibility of the received proposal done by the three RIs selected (preferred) by the user group. Technical problems, risks, and related costs are considered. No further evaluation criteria are employed at this stage.

All received proposals are evaluated by the USP following the principles of transparency, fairness and impartiality. Each proposal is assessed by at least three experts of the USP. The ERIGrid 2.0 Lab Access Manager (i.e., J. Emilio Rodríguez) and the ERIGrid 2.0 Coordinator (i.e., Thomas Strasser) do not participate in the proposal evaluation but are expected to overview the range of submitted proposals and to guarantee the compliance of the proposal with the eligibility rules of the lab access.

There are no meetings of the USP in ERIGrid 2.0; each USP member only keeps a private interaction with the ERIGrid 2.0 Coordinator and the ERIGrid 2.0 Lab Access Manager in order to avoid cross-influences in the evaluations with other USP members. The names of the USP members evaluating a proposal are not known by the proposing user group. On the contrary, the user group members and their organisations are visible in the proposal to be evaluated by the USP (i.e. proposals are not anonymised during their evaluation).

Each USP member reviewing a proposal will evaluate the following categories:

1. *General quality of the proposal (score: 0-10)*: Assessment based on the completeness and organisation of the proposal, clear definition of the objectives and expected results, relevance of the proposed dissemination actions, justified amount of access requested.
2. *Scientific/technical merit (score: 0-10)*: Assessment based on the scientific and technical relevance, originality and innovation, methodology, robust and realistic test/evaluation approach.
3. *Improvement of know-how and capacity of the lab (score: 0-10)*: Assessment based on the improvement of know-how within the laboratories, enhancement of lab technologies and methods, alignment with ERIGrid 2.0 scenarios/use cases/test cases, synergies with other projects and cooperation with other infrastructures.
4. *Compliance with EU policies and priorities (score: 0-10)*: Assessment based on the compliance with European Research and Technological Development (RTD) policies and priorities, social impact, impact on EU industry (e.g., standardisation and competitiveness), sustainable growth interest, new users that have not previously used the installation, users working in countries where no equivalent RI exist, young researchers, female researchers.

For each proposal, the USP expert issues a score, which is the average of the scores of the four individual categories, expressed as total points out of 100. All the categories have the same weight. The final score of the proposal is calculated as the mean value of the scores issued by the USP members evaluating the proposal. Additionally, in this phase, the USP

may provide comments and suggestions to improve the project implementation in the lab (if the proposal is accepted in the end) or build a better proposal for re-submission to future calls (if the proposal is rejected in the current call). A Proposal Review Report is prepared based on the evaluation information of the USP members and sent to the user group when notifying the proposal evaluation result (accepted or rejected). An example of this Proposal Evaluation Report is attached in the Appendix.

Besides the USP evaluation, all proposals are also checked for plagiarism (in accordance with the general H2020 strategy³). Proposals with an unjustified high amount of similarity will not be considered for realisation and will be rejected.

4.2 User Selection Panel Membership

The USP is a group of 133 members from international organisations (“external experts”) and from ERIGrid 2.0 partners (“internal experts”) with diverse profiles (academia, industry) and covering the different domains of the smart energy system arena (power systems, heating networks, Information and Communications Technology (ICT), cybersecurity, etc.).

At the moment, the USP is formed by 77 external experts and 56 internal experts. The presence of “internal experts” is advisable and contributes to assess better if the received proposals are aligned with ERIGrid 2.0 approaches and goals.

Current members of the USP are included in Table 1.

Table 1: Membership of the ERIGrid 2.0 User Selection Panel.

EXTERNAL EXPERTS			
1	Abdulrahman Alassi	IBERDROLA	Qatar
2	Mihaela Albu	Politehnica University of Bucharest	Romania
3	João Francisco Alves Martins	Universidade Nova de Lisboa	Portugal
4	Reza Arghandeh	Western Norway University of Applied Sciences	Norway
5	Davood Babazadeh	Technische Universität Hamburg	Germany
6	Seddik Bacha	G2elab - UGA	France
7	Manuel Barragan-Villarejo	University of Seville	Spain
8	Andrea Benigni	Forschungszentrum Jülich	Germany
9	Yvon Besanger-Moleres	Grenoble INP - UGA	France
10	Theo Bosma	DNVGL	Norway
11	Aggelos Bouhouras	Technological Educational Institute of Western Macedonia	Greece
12	Jose Antonio Bregel	LCOE-FFII	Spain
13	Tiago Castelo de Oliveira	TU Eindhoven	Netherlands
14	Geraint Chaffey	KU Leuven	Belgium
15	Georgios C. Christoforidis	University of Western Macedonia	Greece
16	Giovanni De Carne	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	Germany
17	Marialaura Di Somma	ENEA	Italy
18	Luca Ferrarini	Politecnico di Milano	Italy

³https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/checks-audits-reviews-investigations_en.htm

EXTERNAL EXPERTS

19	Davide Fioriti	Univesità di Pisa	Italy
20	Alemayehu Gebremedhin	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	Norway
21	Joern Geisbuesch	Academia	Germany
22	Murat Gol	Middle East Technical University	Turkey
23	Tasos Gregoriou	Distribution System Operator Cyprus	Cyprus
24	Efren Guillo Sansano	ENERCOOP	Spain
25	Ulf Häger	TU Dortmund	Germany
26	Trevor Hardy	Pacific Northwest National Laboratory	USA
27	Arjen Jongepier	Stedin	Netherlands
28	Petr Kadera	Czech Technical University in Prague	Czech Republic
29	Stavros Karagiannopoulos	ETH	Switzerland
30	Ata Khavari	SIEMENS	Germany
31	Heybet Kilic	Dicle University	Turkey
32	Nand Kishor	Ostfold University College	Norway
33	Thyge Knüppel	SIEMENS GAMESA	Denmark
34	Eleftherios Kontis	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	Greece
35	Anna Kosek	TNO	Belgium
36	Konstantinos Kotsalos	EUROPEAN DYNAMICS	Greece
37	Athanasios Krontiris	Hochschule Darmstadt University of Applied Sciences	Germany
38	Anna Kulmala	ABB	Finland
39	Hannu Laaksonen	University of Vaasa	Finland
40	Luiz Fernando Labado Villa	LAAS CNRS	France
41	Ilias Lamprinos	Intracom SA Telecom Solutions	Greece
42	Yannis Mantzaris	IPTO	Greece
43	Sergio Martinez	Technical University of Madrid	Spain
44	Jose Maria Maza-Ortega	University of Seville	Spain
45	Mark McGranaghan	EPRI	USA
46	Ali Mehrizi-Sani	Virginia Tech	USA
47	Mike Mekkanen	University of Vaasa	Finland
48	Konstantina Mentesidi	Cyprus Transmission System Operator	Greece
49	Andrea Morotti	Unareti	Italy
50	Panagiotis Moutis	Carnegie Mellon University	USA
51	Matija Naglic	TenneT TSO	Netherlands
52	Pedro Nardelli	LUT University	Finland
53	Tung Lam Nguyen	University of Science and Technology of Danang	Vietnam
54	Van Hoa Nguyen	EDF Lab Paris-Saclay	France
55	Artjoms Obusevs	Zurich University of Applied Science	Switzerland
56	Ioannis Panapakidis	University of Thessaly	Greece
57	Theofilos Papadopoulos	Democritus University of Thrace	Greece
58	Nick Papanikolaou	Democritus University of Thrace	Greece
59	Haris Patsios	University of Newcastle	United Kingdom
60	Luigi Piegari	DEIB - Politecnico di Milano	Italy

EXTERNAL EXPERTS

61	Mahdi Pourakbari Kasmaei	Aalto University	Finland
62	Edris Poursmaeil	Aalto University	Finland
63	Victor Sanchez	MEGACAL INSTRUMENTS IBÉRICA	Spain
64	Mohamed Shalaby	Sono Motors GmbH	Germany
65	Pierluigi Siano	University of Salerno	Italy
66	Katja Sirviö	University of Vaasa	Finland
67	Spyros Skarvelis-Kazakos	University of Sussex	United Kingdom
68	Anurag Srivastava	Washington State University	USA
69	Andreas Stavrou	Electricity Authority of Cyprus	Cyprus
70	Yin Sun	Shell	Netherlands
71	Juergen Sutterlueti	Gantner Instruments GmbH	Austria
72	Petr Toman	Brno University of Technology	Czech Republic
73	Philip Top	Lawrence Livermore National Lab	USA
74	Xiaoyu Wang	Carleton University	Canada
75	Yu Wang	Nanyang Technological University	Singapore
76	Stephen Wolthusen	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	Norway
77	Dongsheng Yang	TU Eindhoven	Netherlands

INTERNAL EXPERTS

1	Ibrahim Abdulhadi	University of Strathclyde	United Kingdom
2	Gunter Arnold	Fraunhofer IEE	Germany
3	I. Safak Bayram	University of Strathclyde	United Kingdom
4	Henrik Bindner	Technical University of Denmark	Denmark
5	Ron Brandl	Fraunhofer IEE	Germany
6	Roland Bründlinger	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology	Austria
7	Hervé Buttin	CEA	France
8	Mihai Calin	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology	Austria
9	Salvador Ceballos	TECNALIA	Spain
10	Milos Cetkovic	TUD	Netherlands
11	Alexandros Chronis	ICCS-NTUA	Greece
12	Salvatore D'Arco	SINTEF Energi AS	Norway
13	Pratyush Das	OFFIS	Germany
14	Erik de Jong	KEMA	Netherlands
15	Venizelos Efthymiou	University of Cyprus	Cyprus
16	Corentin Evens	VTT	Finland
17	Chiara Gandolfi	RSE	Italy
18	Oliver Gehrke	Technical University of Denmark	Denmark
19	George Georghiou	University of Cyprus	Cyprus
20	Ian Gilbert	OCT-Ormazabal	Spain
21	Amaia González-Garrido	TECNALIA	Spain
22	Wolfram Heckmann	Fraunhofer IEE	Germany
23	Kai Heussen	Technical University of Denmark	Denmark
24	Tran-The Hoang	CEA	France
25	Josu Izagirre	OCT-Ormazabal	Spain

INTERNAL EXPERTS

26	Joseba Jimeno	TECNALIA	Spain
27	Jirapa Kamsamrong	OFFIS	Germany
28	Panagiotis Karafotis	HEDNO	Greece
29	Alkistis Kontou	ICCS-NTUA	Greece
30	Evangelos Kotsakis	Joint Research Centre of the European Commission	Italy
31	Panos Kotsampopoulos	ICCS-NTUA	Greece
32	Andreas Kyprianou	University of Cyprus	Cyprus
33	Georg Lauss	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology	Austria
34	Kari Mäki	VTT	Finland
35	Savvas Manikas	HEDNO	Greece
36	Olve Mo	SINTEF Energi AS	Norway
37	John Nikolettatos	CRES	Greece
38	Iñaki Orue	OCT-Ormazabal	Spain
39	Rafael Pena-Alzola	University of Strathclyde	United Kingdom
40	Marjan Popov	TUD	Netherlands
41	Filip Pröbstl Andrén	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology	Austria
42	Leonard Enrique Ramos Perez	DERlab e.V.	Germany
43	Kalle Rauma	VTT	Finland
44	Evangelos Rikos	CRES	Greece
45	Sebastian Rohjans	OFFIS / Jade University of Applied Science	Germany
46	Marco Rossi	RSE	Italy
47	Jose Rueda	TUD	Netherlands
48	Santiago Sánchez Acebedo	SINTEF Energi AS	Norway
49	Iolanda Saviuc	Joint Research Centre of the European Commission	Italy
50	Dimitrios Stratogiannis	HEDNO	Greece
51	Diana Strauss-Mincu	DERlab e.V.	Germany
52	Henning Taxt	SINTEF Energi AS	Norway
53	Carlo Tornelli	RSE	Italy
54	Quoc Tuan Tran	CEA	France
55	Peter Vaessen	KEMA	Netherlands
56	John Vlachos	CRES	Greece

The composition of the USP has been kept quite stable since it was created for the evaluation of the 1st call for lab access proposal in October 2020. Obviously, there have been some replacements for different reasons; lack of real availability, retirement, movement to other companies, etc. An updated list of the membership of the USP is maintained by ERIGrid 2.0 and it is at the disposal of the EC.

4.3 User Selection Panel Evaluations of Lab Access Proposals

The following sections include the assignment of USP members to the proposals received in the lab access calls and the corresponding scores cast by them. The aim was to have at least 3 evaluations per proposal to provide a balanced assessment, avoiding any individual bias.

4.3.1 Evaluation of 1st Call Proposals

The following list shows the evaluation results of the 1st call.

1. **PMU-FFR: APPROVED** (65.7/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4
Questions		A. Srivastava	M. Naglic	V. Nguyen	J. Geisbuesch
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	7	9
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	8	6	5
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	6	6	5
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	6	6	8
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	10	6	6
Total points (out of 100)		68	75	60	60

2. **DEFINIT 2.0: APPROVED** (73.8/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5
Questions		A. Benigni	U. Häger	P. Toman	E. Rikos	Y. Mantzaris
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		4	8	10	9	7
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	4	8	10	9
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	4	8	8	6
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	6	7	9	7
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	3	9	10	9
Total points (out of 100)		75	43	80	93	78

3. **COLOUR-POWER: APPROVED** (77.2/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5
Questions		P. Top	F. Prösti Andrén	M. Albu	A. Kyprianou	M. Calin
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		3	4	9	7	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	8	8	6	8
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	7	9	7	7
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	7	8	5	7
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	10	10	6	10
Total points (out of 100)		78	80	88	60	80

4. **Autonom**: APPROVED (69/100)

Overview of Reviews

Questions		Review 1 N. Kishor	Review 2 Y. Wang	Review 3 J. Jimeno	Review 4 H. Laaksonen
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	8	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	2	8	9	8
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	4	8	9	8
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	4	6	8	7
General quality of the proposal	25%	4	8	9	8
Total points (out of 100)		35	75	88	78

5. **POLARIS**: APPROVED (81.6/100)

Overview of Reviews

Questions		Review 1 T. Knüppel	Review 2 L. Piegari	Review 3 J. Maza-Ortega	Review 4 S. D'Arco	Review 5 N. Papanikolaou
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	9	8	10	10
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	9	9	8	8
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	9	9	9	8
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	9	9	6	4
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	9	9	9	9
Total points (out of 100)		75	90	90	80	73

6. **SES-MGES**: APPROVED (57.2/100)

Overview of Reviews

Questions		Review 1 S. Rohjans	Review 2 P. Kadera	Review 3 L. Ferrarini	Review 4 W. Heckmann
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	7	8	5
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	1	5	9
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	9	1	8	8
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	0	6	7
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	1	6	8
Total points (out of 100)		78	8	63	80

7. **Hytechnet**: APPROVED (62.7/100)

Overview of Reviews

Questions		Review 1 P. Moutis	Review 2 A. Jongepier	Review 3 M. Shalaby	Review 4 K. Mentessidi
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		6	7	6	4
Scientific/technical merit	25%	4	7	8	7
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	2	9	8	6
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	4	9	7	7
General quality of the proposal	25%	1	6	7	8
Total points (out of 100)		28	78	75	70

8. **M-ECHall: APPROVED** (57/100)

Questions		Review 1 I. Saviuc	Review 2 A. Chronis	Review 3 H. Klic	Review 4 E. de Jong	Review 5 M. Calin	Review 6 L. Labado Villa
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	9	10	9	9	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	7	2	4	7	7
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	9	0	4	8	8
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	7	0	5	7	6
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	9	2	6	7	6
Total points (out of 100)		63	80	10	48	73	68

9. **BAMLEV: NOT APPROVED** (51.7/100)

Questions		Review 1 T. Gregoriou	Review 2 I. Bayram	Review 3 A. Obusevs	Review 4 I. Panapakidis
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	8	7	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	4	5	6
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	6	3	7
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	3	3	6
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	2	4	6
Total points (out of 100)		68	38	38	63

Note: This proposal failed the plagiarism check.

10. **RT-SimVal: APPROVED** (60.7/100)

Questions		Review 1 J. Alves Martins	Review 2 Y. Besanger-Moleres	Review 3 M. Popov	Review 4 G. De Carne
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	8	10	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	5	8	7	4
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	5	8	7	6
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	6	6	7
General quality of the proposal	25%	5	8	6	4
Total points (out of 100)		50	75	65	53

11. **OEM-MGR: NOT APPROVED** (47/100)

Questions		Review 1 K. Sirviö	Review 2 X. Wang	Review 3 A. Marinopoulos	Review 4 M. Calin
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	8	8	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	3	4	7	4
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	3	6	6	5
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	4	4	7	5
General quality of the proposal	25%	3	4	6	4
Total points (out of 100)		33	45	65	45

4.3.2 Evaluation of 2nd Call Proposals

The following list shows the evaluation results of the 2nd call.

1. **DPSSEC: NOT APPROVED** (57/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3
Questions		M. Gol	U. Hager	S. Manikas
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	8	4
Scientific/technical merit	25%	4	5	5
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	5	7	7
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	6	9
General quality of the proposal	25%	3	5	6
Total points (out of 100)		45	58	68

Note: Proposal too vague for lab implementation. Important issues raised by the USP.

2. **PROOF: APPROVED** (74.5/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4
Questions		L. Labado Villa	T. Hoang	E. Rikos	W. Heckmann
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	9	7	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	6	10	7
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	6	8	8
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	7	9	7
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	6	9	8
Total points (out of 100)		70	63	90	75

3. **VoIDIP: APPROVED** (65.3/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3
Questions		P. Moutis	G. De Carne	A. González-Garrido
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	9	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	4	9
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	4	8
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	5	6
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	4	8
Total points (out of 100)		75	43	78

4. **DeMaDsVal: APPROVED** (81/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4
Questions		J. Alves Martins	P. Top	P. Toman	A. Khavari
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	6	8	6
Scientific/technical merit	25%	10	6	8	8
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	10	7	8	8
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	6	7	7
General quality of the proposal	25%	10	8	8	10
Total points (out of 100)		95	68	78	83

5. **GRIDPV100: APPROVED** (74.8/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5
Questions		I. Saviuc	G. Christoforidis	E. Poursmaeil	J. Maza-Ortega	M. Albu
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		6	8	10	9	9
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	9	5	7	9
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	8	7	8	8
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	8	4	9	7
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	9	5	8	9
Total points (out of 100)		73	85	53	80	83

6. **DynOMO: NOT APPROVED** (53.7/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3
Questions		Y. Mantzaris	T. Papadopoulos	E. de Jong
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		6	7	9
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	5	4
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	8	2
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	6	4
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	4	2
Total points (out of 100)		73	58	30

Note: Proposal not ready for lab implementation yet. Important issues raised by the USP.

7. **SIM HES-OFF: APPROVED** (72/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4
Questions		A. Benigni	V. Nguyen	E. Kontis	P. Kadera
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	10	7	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	4	6	8	8
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	6	8	8
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	6	6	8
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	8	10	9
Total points (out of 100)		60	65	80	83

8. **PPiF: APPROVED** (71.3/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3
Questions		A. Obusevs	K. Anastasakis	V. Efthymiou
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	6	10
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	10	5
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	10	4
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	9	5
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	10	5
Total points (out of 100)		68	98	48

9. *Open-CANVerter*: **APPROVED** (76.2/100)

Questions		Review 1 L. Ferrarini	Review 2 M. Mekkanen	Review 3 Y. Wang	Review 4 S. Skarvelis-Kazakos	Review 5 E. Kotsakis
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	8	8	8	9
Scientific/technical merit	25%	5	9	6	8	9
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	9	7	7	8
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	7	7	6	8
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	9	6	8	9
Total points (out of 100)		73	85	65	73	85

10. *VaFlexPot*: **APPROVED** (69.3/100)

Questions		Review 1 K. Sirvio	Review 2 Y. Sun	Review 3 G. Lauss
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	6	9
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	6	8
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	9	6	9
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	2	6
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	6	8
Total points (out of 100)		80	50	78

11. *CREAM*: **APPROVED** (79.5/100)

Questions		Review 1 I. Panapakidis	Review 2 D. Babazadeh	Review 3 T. Gregoriou	Review 4 F. Pröbstl Andrén
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		6	9	7	7
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	6	9	8
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	7	9	8
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	7	9	6
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	8	10	8
Total points (out of 100)		80	70	93	75

12. *PVinPS*: **APPROVED** (65.7/100)

Questions		Review 1 A. Jongepier	Review 2 L. Piegari	Review 3 J. Sutterlueti	Review 4 A. Kulmala
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	9	6	6
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	6	5	7
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	8	5	7
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	7	5	8
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	7	5	8
Total points (out of 100)		68	70	50	75

13. **ResiMG: APPROVED** (68.2/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4
Questions		Y. Besanger-Moleres			
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	9	8	9
Scientific/technical merit	25%	10	7	6	4
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	10	8	8	5
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	6	6	4
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	9	8	3
Total points (out of 100)		88	75	70	40

4.3.3 Evaluation of 3rd Call Proposals

The following list shows the evaluation results of the 3rd call.

1. **PETER: APPROVED** (61.7/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3
Questions		M. Naglic		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		4	8	7
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	7	7
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	6	7
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	6	6
General quality of the proposal	25%	2	5	6
Total points (out of 100)		60	60	65

2. **FLEVOEWIM: APPROVED** (75.3/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3
Questions		J. Alves Martins		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	6	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	7	9
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	7	8
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	7	7
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	9	9
Total points (out of 100)		68	75	83

3. **VEHICLE: APPROVED** (66/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3
Questions		N. Papanikolaou		
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	7	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	9	4	6
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	9	6	5
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	6	6
General quality of the proposal	25%	10	6	4
Total points (out of 100)		90	55	53

4.3.4 Evaluation of 4th Call Proposals

The following list shows the evaluation results of the 4th call.

1. **PMUs-Cloud: APPROVED** (65.2/100)

Questions		Review 1 S. D'Arco	Review 2 M. Albu	Review 3 M. Naglic	Review 4 E. Kontis	Review 5 E. de Jong
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	10	8	9	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	3	9	6	8	8
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	4	9	6	8	6
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	7	6	6	8
General quality of the proposal	25%	2	5	7	8	8
Total points (out of 100)		38	75	63	75	75

2. **VOLTMETER: NOT APPROVED** (52/100)

Questions		Review 1 I. Bayram	Review 2 A. Kulmala	Review 3 M. Calin
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		6	10	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	5	5	5
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	4	6	5
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	6	5
General quality of the proposal	25%	5	6	5
Total points (out of 100)		48	58	50

Note: Important issues raised by the USP do not allow the lab implementation.

3. **DynOMO: APPROVED** (68/100)

Questions		Review 1 T. Papadopoulos	Review 2 G. Arnold	Review 3 M. Calin
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	7	7
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	7	6
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	8	8
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	6	6
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	6	7
Total points (out of 100)		68	68	68

4. **AIDGRIDS: APPROVED** (81/100)

Questions		Review 1 M. Gol	Review 2 S. Rohjans	Review 3 A. González-Garrido
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	7	9
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	9	10
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	10	8
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	8	7
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	10	9
Total points (out of 100)		65	93	85

5. **CybTEST: APPROVED** (72/100)

Overview of Reviews

Questions		Review 1 D. Babazadeh	Review 2 A. Obusevs	Review 3 J. Nikolettos	Review 4 A. Khavari
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	6	8	6
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	6	6	7
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	9	6	7	7
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	6	7	7
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	7	8	7
Total points (out of 100)		85	63	70	70

6. **LD-RTCosim: APPROVED** (64.8/100)

Overview of Reviews

Questions		Review 1 R. Brandl	Review 2 J. Geisbuesch	Review 3 V. Nguyen	Review 4 G. Lauss	Review 5 A. Kontou	Review 6 E. Guillo Sansano
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	9	10	9	10
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	4	7	7	7	7
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	3	8	6	9	8
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	4	5	6	6	6
General quality of the proposal	25%	4	3	8	8	10	8
Total points (out of 100)		63	35	70	68	80	73

7. **SMPS: APPROVED** (60.7/100)

Overview of Reviews

Questions		Review 1 K. Sirvio	Review 2 T. Gregoriou	Review 3 H. Laaksonen	Review 4 T. Hoang	Review 5 R. Pena-Alzola	Review 6 I. Abdulhadi
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	6	8	8	9	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	3	9	7	7	2	7
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	5	9	7	7	1	8
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	7	6	9	2	6
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	8	8	6	1	7
Total points (out of 100)		53	83	70	73	15	70

8. **AGIPDem: APPROVED** (72.4/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5
Questions		G. De Carne	S. Bacha	J. Maza-Ortega	I. Orue	S. Ceballos
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	7	8	8	5
Scientific/technical merit	25%	9	8	7	5	7
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	8	7	8	8
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	6	7	5	7
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	7	7	7	7
Total points (out of 100)		83	73	70	63	73

9. **HCEQIS: NOT APPROVED** (49/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4
Questions		H. Kilic	L. Labado Villa	N. Kishor	T. Hoang
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	9	8	6
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	4	4	4
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	4	7	4
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	4	4	6	6
General quality of the proposal	25%	4	5	6	4
Total points (out of 100)		50	43	58	45

10. **RCPIso: APPROVED** (59.2/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5
Questions		Y. Besanger-Moleres	I. Saviuc	P. Nardelli	K. Anastasakis	C. Tomelli
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		6	8	9	6	10
Scientific/technical merit	25%	4	6	6	7	6
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	8	7	6	4
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	6	7	5	3
General quality of the proposal	25%	5	6	7	7	7
Total points (out of 100)		50	65	68	63	50

11. **IoRE: NOT APPROVED** (45.3/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3
Questions		E. Pouresmaeil	H. Taxt	V. Efthymiou
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	6	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	9	1	2
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	2	4
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	2	4
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	2	3
Total points (out of 100)		85	18	33

12. IC2PSofMG: APPROVED (59/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4	Review 5
Questions		L. Ferrarini	N. Papanikolaou	C. Gandolfi	M. Rossi	A. González-Garrido
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	10	9	7	9
Scientific/technical merit	25%	5	6	5	6	4
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	7	5	7	7
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	6	5	6	6
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	7	7	7	5
Total points (out of 100)		55	65	55	65	55

13. SEFL EMTR: APPROVED (84.3/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3
Questions		U. Hager	S. Martinez	E. de Jong
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	6	6
Scientific/technical merit	25%	9	9	7
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	9	8	7
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	9	7	9
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	9	9
Total points (out of 100)		90	83	80

14. TRMDRO: APPROVED (75.7/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4
Questions		J. Alves Martins	L. Piegari	M. Shalaby	K. Maki
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	10	5	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	7	9	7
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	6	9	8
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	8	8	7
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	7	6	8
Total points (out of 100)		78	70	80	75

15. CYPRESS: APPROVED (77.7/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3
Questions		E. Rikos	G. Fulli	P. Kadera
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	6	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	9	8	8
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	9	8	6
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	7	7
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	7	7
Total points (out of 100)		88	75	70

16. **RELENDER: APPROVED** (74/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4
Questions		A. Benigni	F. Pröbstl Andrén	P. Kotsampopoulos	A. Kyprianou
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	6	7
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	9	8	8
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	8	7	9
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	8	7	8
General quality of the proposal	25%	4	9	7	8
Total points (out of 100)		55	85	73	83

4.3.5 Evaluation of 5th Call Proposals

The following list shows the evaluation results of the 5th call.

1. **Grid ExpandER: APPROVED** (71/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3
Questions		M. Gol	P. Toman	T. Papadopoulos
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	8	7
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	8	5
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	8	6
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	8	5
General quality of the proposal	25%	10	8	4
Total points (out of 100)		83	80	50

2. **CPHILT-GFVSC: APPROVED** (76.7/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3	Review 4
Questions		S. D'Arco	G. Lauss	E. de Jong	A. González-Garrido
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	10	10	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	7	9	8
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	6	8	9
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	7	7	6
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	7	9	8
Total points (out of 100)		78	68	83	78

3. **PHIL-Rep: APPROVED** (58.3/100)

Overview of Reviews		Review 1	Review 2	Review 3
Questions		V. Nguyen	G. Lauss	J. Geisbuesch
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		9	10	10
Scientific/technical merit	25%	4	7	5
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	2	8	6
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	6	8
General quality of the proposal	25%	4	7	7
Total points (out of 100)		40	70	65

4. **EMS4GCHS: APPROVED** (50.7/100)

Overview of Reviews

Questions		Review 1 P. Moutis	Review 2 M. Mekkanen	Review 3 T. Gregoriou	Review 4 S. Skarvelis-Kazakos
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	8	7	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	2	4	6	8
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	4	4	7	7
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	2	6	7	7
General quality of the proposal	25%	0	4	6	7
Total points (out of 100)		20	45	65	73

5. **HIHREMS: APPROVED** (55.3/100)

Overview of Reviews

Questions		Review 1 L. Labado Villa	Review 2 E. Rikos	Review 3 A. Kontou
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	10	7
Scientific/technical merit	25%	3	7	7
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	1	7	7
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	2	8	8
General quality of the proposal	25%	1	7	8
Total points (out of 100)		18	73	75

6. **ProMiSe: APPROVED** (80.2/100)

Overview of Reviews

Questions		Review 1 A. Jongepier	Review 2 X. Wang	Review 3 A. Obusevs	Review 4 A. Kulmala
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	8	8	9
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	8	7	7
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	10	8	8	8
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	8	8	7	6
General quality of the proposal	25%	10	9	8	8
Total points (out of 100)		90	83	75	73

7. **PERFECT: APPROVED** (63.6/100)

Overview of Reviews

Questions		Review 1 L. Ferrarini	Review 2 U. Häger	Review 3 R. Arghandeh	Review 4 E. de Jong	Review 5 S. Ceballos
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		6	8	9	10	5
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	6	6	6	7
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	8	7	5	7
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	6	6	6	7
General quality of the proposal	25%	8	6	7	7	4
Total points (out of 100)		65	65	65	60	63

8. **CyDERFORT: APPROVED** (77.5/100)

Overview of Reviews

Questions		Review 1 D. Babazadeh	Review 2 P. Nardelli	Review 3 S. Rohjans	Review 4 G. Lauss
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	8	6	5
Scientific/technical merit	25%	8	9	8	6
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	9	8	6
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	9	7	6
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	9	9	6
Total points (out of 100)		80	90	80	60

9. **IETGPSC: APPROVED** (49.7/100)

Overview of Reviews

Questions		Review 1 I. Saviuc	Review 2 N. Kishor	Review 3 S. Martinez
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		7	8	7
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	2	5
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	4	5
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	3	7
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	2	6
Total points (out of 100)		63	28	58

10. **DynaPEM: APPROVED** (57.2/100)

Overview of Reviews

Questions		Review 1 G. De Carne	Review 2 Y. Besanger-Moleres	Review 3 L. Piegari	Review 4 E. Kontis	Review 5 H. Laaksonen
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	8	8	8	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	8	4	6	5
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	8	4	5	5
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	6	6	5	5
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	8	4	5	6
Total points (out of 100)		60	75	45	53	53

11. **Multigridcon: APPROVED** (63.3/100)

Overview of Reviews

Questions		Review 1 N. Papanikolaou	Review 2 H. Kilic	Review 3 Y. Wang
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		10	10	9
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	6	6
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	7	6	7
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	7	6	5
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	6	6
Total points (out of 100)		70	60	60

4.3.6 Evaluation of 6th Call Proposals

The following list shows the evaluation results of the 6th call.

1. **TRMDRO: APPROVED** (67/100)

Overview of Reviews									
Questions		Review 1 J. Alves Martins	Review 2 G. De Carne	Review 3 S. Bacha	Review 4 T. Knüppel	Review 5 J. Bregel	Review 6 A. Alassi Refused to Review	Review 7 E. Rikos	Review 8 P. Kotsampopoulos
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		8	--	--	--	--	--	8	5
Scientific/technical merit	25%	6	--	--	--	--	--	9	7
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	--	--	--	--	--	8	5
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	5	--	--	--	--	--	7	5
General quality of the proposal	25%	7	--	--	--	--	--	7	8
Total points (out of 100)		60	--	--	--	--	--	78	63

2. **ISAIPS: APPROVED** (76.8/100)

Overview of Reviews							
Questions		Review 1 U. Häger	Review 2 X. Wang	Review 3 P. Top	Review 4 A. Khavari	Review 5 A. Bouhouras	Review 6 D. Yang
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		6	6	4	--	7	10
Scientific/technical merit	25%	9	8	6	--	9	8
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	8	7	6	--	8	7
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	9	8	6	--	8	7
General quality of the proposal	25%	9	8	6	--	8	8
Total points (out of 100)		88	78	60	--	83	75

3. **FaultTS: APPROVED** (67.7/100)

Overview of Reviews							
Questions		Review 1 M. Naglic Refused to Review	Review 2 P. Toman	Review 3 A. Stavrou	Review 4 T. Papadopoulos	Review 5 M. Popov	Review 6 I. Gilbert
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		--	8	--	7	9	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	--	6	--	6	6	8
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	--	8	--	7	7	7
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	--	6	--	5	7	7
General quality of the proposal	25%	--	8	--	4	7	9
Total points (out of 100)		--	70	--	55	68	78

4. Sono LV-MCU: APPROVED (68.2/100)

Questions		Review 1 H. Patsios	Review 2 L. Labado Villa	Review 3 J. Sutterlueti	Review 4 G. Georghiou	Review 5 K. Rauma	Review 6 M. Di Somma	Review 7 A. Kontou	Review 8 E. de Jong	Review 9 G. Lauss
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		--	8	--	--	--	8	8	10	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	--	7	--	--	--	8	8	3	8
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	--	6	--	--	--	8	8	2	8
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	--	6	--	--	--	6	9	5	7
General quality of the proposal	25%	--	7	--	--	--	8	9	5	8
Total points (out of 100)		--	65	--	--	--	75	85	38	78

5. CTCPM: APPROVED (67.2/100)

Questions		Review 1 D. Fioriti	Review 2 A. Mehrizi-Sani	Review 3 H. Kilic	Review 4 S. Wolthusen	Review 5 W. Heckmann	Review 6 J. Kamsamrong
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		4	10	8	--	4	6
Scientific/technical merit	25%	7	8	4	--	7	8
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	6	8	4	--	7	8
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	6	7	4	--	7	7
General quality of the proposal	25%	6	8	6	--	7	9
Total points (out of 100)		63	78	45	--	70	80

6. CYPRESS-Wood: APPROVED (72.2/100)

Questions		Review 1 P. Kadera	Review 2 A. Kroniris	Review 3 M. Barragan-Villarejo	Review 4 T. Hardy	Review 5 A. Gebremedhin Refused to Review	Review 6 K. Kotsalos
Familiarity of the reviewer with the topic		--	6	8	9	--	8
Scientific/technical merit	25%	--	7	7	5	--	9
Improve know-how and capacity of the lab	25%	--	8	8	4	--	9
Compliance with EU policies and priorities	25%	--	7	6	6	--	8
General quality of the proposal	25%	--	8	8	6	--	9
Total points (out of 100)		--	75	73	53	--	88

5 Lab Access User Workshops

As part of the dissemination and communication actions in ERIGrid 2.0, two user workshops are foreseen during the course of the project with the objective of presenting the lab access project results and facilitating the exchange and feedback within the user groups, consortium members and other stakeholders.

The first user workshop will be organised online in mid-September 2023. A first bunch of exemplary user projects will be selected for presentation to an international audience, sharing experiences and problems found during the access process and lab implementations. The intention is to organise these workshops as “mini-conferences”.

The second user workshop will take place at the end of the project, probably integrated within the ERIGrid 2.0 Final Event, to be held face-to-face in Vienna, Austria, in September 2024.

Outcomes from these two workshops will be reported in the upcoming Deliverable D6.6 (due at the end of the project), in an update of the information contained in this report at the end of ERIGrid 2.0.

6 Provision of Lab Access

6.1 Summary of Lab Access Achievements and Outlook

Considering the situation of the first 6 calls for lab access proposals described in the above sections, the provision of access is the following:

- 60 proposals received.
- 33 projects already implemented in the RI:
 - 572 access days (of the targeted 1693 access days: final objective indicated in the Grant Agreement): 34% of the committed access days.
 - 72 users.
 - 4 industrial projects (12% of the total projects).
 - 192 access days provided to users from non-EU organisations (11% of the final objective for the total access provision: 1693 access days).
 - 60 access days corresponding to ERIGrid 2.0 partners (“internal lab access”).

If, in addition to the first 6 calls, the recently evaluated 7th call is also included (i.e., considering all the evaluated proposals until the date of this deliverable that have been accepted by the USP and are feasible for implementation in the lab), the above numbers are updated as follows:

- 85 proposals received.
- 65 projects already implemented or waiting for implementation in the lab.
- 1107 access days (65% of the of the final objective for the total access provision).
- 147 users.
- 13 industrial projects (20% of the total projects).
- Non-EU proposals:
 - 28 proposals have come from non-EU countries: India (12), Colombia (4), UK (3), Pakistan (2), USA (1), Japan (1), Brazil (1), Iran (1), South Africa (1), Egypt (1), Jordan (1).
 - 478 access days (28% of the final objective for the total access provision).
- Internal lab access: 80 access days in 3 projects between ERIGrid 2.0 partners (5% of the total access days).
- Multi-RI projects: 3 multisite projects (PViNPS uses 3 RIs, AIDGRIDS uses 2 RIs, and AGIPDem uses 2 RIs).

6.2 Degree of Provision

Further to the overall numbers of the previous section, this section describes in more detail the provision of lab access and the degree of accomplishment of the commitments by the ERIGrid 2.0 partners up to the date of submission of this deliverable.

The Grant Agreement (GA) (*ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement, 2019*) states the minimum quantity of access to be provided by each installation in terms of access days. Figure 4 below also includes an estimation of the corresponding number of user projects and users linked to the access days.

Access provider short name	Short name of infrastructure	Installation		Installation Country code	Type of access	Unit of access	Unit cost (UC) (€)	Min. quantity of access to be provided	Access costs		Estimated number of users	Estimated number of user projects
		No	Short name						On the basis of UC	As actual costs		
AIT	SmartEST Lab	1	SmartEST	AT	TA-ac	day		200		147.500,00	32	14
CRES	PV&DGLab	3	PV&DGLab	GR	TA-uc	day	1.203,47	80	96.277,60		14	7
DTU	PowerlabDK	4	SYSLAB/ESSL	DK	TA-ac	day		80		160.700,00	16	8
TUD	ESE-Lab	6	ESE-Lab	NL	TA-uc	day	1.990,00	60	119.400,00		10	5
KEMA	FPGL	7	FPGL	NL	TA-uc	day	6.875,00	20	137.500,00		8	4
IEE	SysTec	8	SysTec	DE	TA-ac	day		75		138.635,95	10	5
HEDNO	L&RS-lab	9	L&RS-lab	GR	TA-uc	day	518,38	15	7.775,70		4	2
HEDNO	SGC-LAB	10	SGC-LAB	GR	TA-uc	day	585,00	10	5.850,00		4	2
ICCS	EES-lab	12	EES-lab	GR	TA-uc	day	1.800,64	108	194.469,12		16	8
JRC	SGILab	14	SGILAB-PTT	NL	TA-ac	day		100		91.250,00	14	7
JRC	SGILab	15	SGILAB-IPR	IT	TA-ac	day		100		91.250,00	14	7
OFFIS	SESA-Lab	16	SESA-Lab	DE	TA-ac	day		75		81.875,00	10	5
OCT	UDEX	18	UDEX	ES	TA-uc	day	5.638,06	40	225.522,40		10	5
RSE	DER-TF	19	DER-TF	IT	TA-uc	day	2.762,00	75	207.150,00		16	8
RWTH	RTLab	21	RTLab	DE	TA-ac	day		120		94.365,00	12	6
SINTEF	NSGL	23	NSGL	NO	TA-ac	day		105		144.331,25	14	7
TECNALIA	SGTL	24	SGTL	ES	TA-ac	day		100		102.187,50	15	6
UCY	LVEM	25	LVEM	CY	TA-ac	day		100		75.000,00	10	5
UoS	DPSL	26	DPSL	UK	TA-uc	day	1.494,83	50	74.741,50		10	5
UoS	PNDC	27	PNDC	UK	TA-uc	day	3.120,00	55	171.600,00		10	5
VTT	MultiPower	29	MultiPower	FI	TA-ac	day		125		124.717,50	20	10
Total								1.693			269	133

Figure 4: Provision of access as stated in the Grant Agreement of ERIGrid 2.0.

Considering the 7 calls evaluated so far, the distribution of lab access days per partner for already implemented projects and accepted projects waiting for implementation is shown in Figure 5. Data are presented with respect to the goals included in the Grant Agreement.

Figure 5: Lab access by installation (already provided and foreseen access days).

Figure 6 represents the same information jointly with the total figures at the project level. In this Deliverable D6.5 [doi:10.5281/zenodo.7968453](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7968453) 46 of 60

representation, it can be seen that approximately 1/3 of the overall access objective has been already provided and another 1/3 is accepted in the pipeline for lab implementation.

Figure 6: Number of access days: total and by installation.

7 Provision of Virtual Access

Unlike ERIGrid⁴, the ERIGrid 2.0 project provides the opportunity to access virtual infrastructures to researchers worldwide. This VA is made available free of charge, to open and freely available resources such as databases, real-time data or simulation platforms. It aims at facilitating casual online access with minimal administrative overheads compared to the more elaborate application and selection process defined in the lab access procedure described in previous sections; in the VA modality there is no need of submitting a proposal, there is no competitive selection of the users through the USP, and there is no mandatory technical report after the access.

At the moment, 10 virtual facilities are operating and can be reached on the ERIGrid 2.0 web page⁵. Figure 7 shows the offered VA services.

Figure 7: Virtual access facilities offered by ERIGrid 2.0.

Deliverable D6.1 (*D-NA5.1 Specification of the Trans-national Access and Virtual Access Programmes*, 2021) provides further description of these virtual facilities, the access procedure, and some associated ancillary tools used to support and monitor these services. VA is assessed every 18 months by a board of international experts; first periodic evaluation has been formalised in Deliverable D6.2 (*D-NA5.2a Virtual Access Assessment Report*, 2021).

The access to the VA infrastructures is not measured as it is in the typical lab access (in terms of “access days” spent in the lab). There is no unit of access defined but some metrics and statistics are collected on the VA activity; quantity of use, geographical distribution of users, etc. ERIGrid 2.0 has implemented web analytic services for users visiting the VA facilities based on the open-source tool Matomo⁶.

7.1 Web Analytics

The data presented in this section has been collected by the web-tracking tool Matomo during a period starting at the beginning of the ERIGrid 2.0 project (April 2020) and ending by September 2022.

⁴<https://erigrd.eu>

⁵<https://erigrd2.eu/lab-access>

⁶<https://matomo.org>

Table 2 ranks the services according to the number of page views and unique visitors. However, a direct comparison of VA services based on these numbers is not justified since not all services have been online at the same time during this analysed period. The proportion of the total VA visitors with respect to the total is 17%, which shows how people interested in the ERIGrid 2.0 project are increasingly using the VA services.

Table 2: Overview of Matomo web-analytics visitors and page-views.

Partner	Facility	Unique Visitors	Page-views
—	ERIGrid 2.0 Mainpage	25,532	81,246
—	VA Support Forum	565	1,873
—	VA User Questionnaire	725	1,982
ICCS	OpenAFPM	2,542	11,967
UoS	Smartgrid MVP	986	2,017
OFFIS	SESA Virt. SIM	559	750
HEDNO	SGRID	469	672
RSE	DER-TF DaaS	439	1,504
RWTH	Vlab	324	958
ICCS	Virtual Lab	173	576
AIT	SmartEST Sim Lab	65	119
DTU	SYSLAB VA	48	100
Sum VA		5,557	18,563
Sum All		32,379	103,664

Figure 8 and Figure 9 show the geographical origin of users visiting the ERIGrid 2.0 VA services. There is a clear involvement of countries from all continents. The proportion of visitors located in European countries is 53.4%. Figure 10 shows the number of unique visitors over the analysed period. Two important peaks can be seen in October of 2020, which correlates with the joint ERIGrid 2.0/PANTERA webinar/workshop in which the VA programme was especially covered; and in February of 2021.

Figure 8: Origins of users as gathered by Matomo analytics based on their IP address.

Figure 9: Origins of users within the EU as gathered by Matomo analytics based on their IP address.

Figure 10: Unique visitor numbers over time for VA services.

Figure 11 lists the social networks which were used to promote the ERIGrid 2.0 services.

Figure 11: Social networks used to promote VA services.

Figure 12 shows the number of visits per unique visitor. It can be seen that there is an important number of recurrent users of the VA infrastructures. It is interesting to do a qualitative analysis by comparing these results to some of the lab access indicators. Particularly important is the minimum duration of a lab access project and the total number of visitors. This minimum duration is currently 5 days. We could sum the total number of VA visits from this point, excluding those “unrealistic” numbers of visits, probably made by bots, which in this case the consortium considers to be starting from 50 visits. This sums to 1,915 unique visitors using the VA services on a recurrent basis. One way to confirm how close this VA use is to the lab access services is through the VA user survey. In any case, through the number of visits, the importance of the VA services for the ERIGrid 2.0 project can be confirmed.

Figure 12: Number of visits by visitors as gathered by Matomo analytics based on their IP address.

7.2 User Questionnaire Inputs

In addition to the automatically collected statistics by the Matomo web analytics tool, VA users are asked to provide additional details on a voluntary basis. In the reporting period, 848 users have provided this information. There were 262 entries with invalid data, which were removed for the current analysis. Approximately half of these users opted-in to participate in an online survey to evaluate the VA services. The results of this survey are available in Deliverable D6.3 (*D-NA5.2b Virtual Access Assessment Report, 2023*).

Figure 13 shows the distribution of the users between the available VA services. Figure 14 shows the distribution of countries from which the users originate based on their own provided inputs.

Figure 13: Distribution of users between services gathered via questionnaire.

Figure 14: Distribution of user home countries gathered via questionnaire.

Figure 15 shows the distribution of these countries after classifying them in EU and non-EU countries. The majority of users have an academic background while only 14% have an industrial background. As shown in Figure 16, this share amounts to 26% if only users of the EU are considered.

Figure 15: Distribution of user origins gathered via questionnaire.

Figure 16: Distribution of European users by institution type.

7.3 Up-time Monitoring

Figure 17 shows the dashboard⁷ of the ERIGrid 2.0 services. This dashboard is accessible to the public and lists all monitored services with their current state and past incidents. Periods of unavailability are indicated by red bars while periods of proper operation are marked in green.

Periods of prolonged downtime, as, for example for the DTU SYSLAB VA or OFFIS SESA Virtual Sim can be explained by delayed provisioning of the service in August 2021.

⁷<https://stats.uptimebot.com/LBVOxFkNWN>

Figure 17: UptimeRobot service dashboard.

8 Conclusions

As described in this report, the lab and virtual access activities in ERIGrid 2.0 are clearly specified and consolidated.

Concerning lab access, 8 calls for proposals have been launched and closed, with 101 proposals received (considering the 8th call recently closed and not evaluated yet) and 85 proposals assessed by a solid USP formed by 133 experts. 33 user projects have already been implemented in the labs with 572 access days (of a total of 1693 access days, i.e. 34%) provided to 72 users.

Roughly speaking, 1/3 of the overall access objective has been already provided; another 1/3 is accepted in the pipeline for lab implementation, and another 1/3 is still to be provided (linked to the future 8th, 9th, and 10th calls until the end of ERIGrid 2.0). Taking into account these figures and considering the upcoming calls until September 2024, the initial lab access goals remain very challenging but can be reached.

As it happened in ERIGrid, at this point of ERIGrid 2.0 some labs are close to having spent their allocated lab access budget, going beyond their initial estimates. Lab access budget exchanges between partners are being considered to address this situation, trying to maximise the provision of access at the project level.

Regarding virtual access, 10 VA services have been provisioned and are now available to users. The ERIGrid 2.0 project website and social media channels have been used to advertise the VA service offerings to the research community. So far, ERIGrid 2.0 VA facilities have offered access to around 5,000 unique visitors, which confirms the importance of the VA services within ERIGrid 2.0 as a helpful complement to the physical lab access (especially in times of reduced services due to the pandemic situation), and the clear benefits when reaching out to the international research community.

The evaluation of the access provision carried out in this report will be updated at the end of ERIGrid 2.0 by means of Deliverable D6.6.

References

D-NA5.1 Specification of the Trans-national Access and Virtual Access Programmes. (2021). Deliverable D6.1, The ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium. doi:[10.5281/zenodo.4450833](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4450833)

D-NA5.2a Virtual Access Assessment Report. (2021). Deliverable D6.2, The ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium.

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ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement. (2019). European Commission.

Appendix: Proposal Review Report

An example of a Proposal Review Report is presented in this section. The proposal/project data have been anonymised (call number, proposal reference, proposal acronym and user group organisation). Reviewers' names are always anonymous to the user. In the review report the individual scores provided by the involved USP experts are stated per category jointly with their specific comments and suggestions for improvement.

The Proposal Review Report was sent by email by the ERIGrid 2.0 proposal submission system⁸ (ConfTool-based) once the proposal has been assessed by the USP and accepted by the ERIGrid 2.0 Management Team.

```
=====
From: ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium <erigrd2@conftool.net>
Sent on: XXXXXXXX
To: XXXXXXXXXXXXX
CC: XXXXXXXXXXXXX
Subject: [ERIGrid 2.0] Lab Access (Xth Call): User Proposal Evaluation Results
=====
```

Dear XXXXXXXXX,

We would like to inform you that your Lab Access user proposal "<Title of the proposal>" (ERIGrid 2.0 Reference: XXX) has been evaluated by the ERIGrid 2.0 User Selection Panel, with the following review details:

PROPOSAL DETAILS

ID: XXX

Proposal: <Title of the proposal>

REVIEW RESULT OF THE USER SELECTION PANEL: This contribution has been accepted.

The assigned lab is "Distributed Energy Resources Test Facility (RSE)".

Please get in contact with the assigned lab through the lab enquiry form or the provided contact information at <https://erigrd2.eu/lab-access/> in order to confirm the feasibility of your project in the lab and organize your stay there.

OVERVIEW OF REVIEWS

Review 1

=====

Evaluation of the Proposal

Merit (25%): 8

Improve know-how (25%): 9

Compliance (25%): 7

General quality (25%): 9

Total points (out of 100): 83

⁸<https://conftool.com/erigrd2>

Comments for the Authors

The project proposal is very well prepared, the target is clearly defined and the process is described step by step in details. The expected results would be beneficial for the community. The question could be if the proposed techniques/items to simulate failure modes are really faithfully corresponding with real PV failures. Probably some work was done but it is not directly referenced in the first part of chapter 3 where the items for failure simulation are introduced. According my opinion the comparison with real failures could be done before. There should be possible collect panels with developing failures which are able test. On other side the proposed techniques to simulate failure modes are corresponding with expected behavior of PV panel with faults described from physics point of view. I recommend the proposal for acceptance.

Review 2

=====

Evaluation of the Proposal

Merit (25%): 6
 Improve know-how (25%): 7
 Compliance (25%): 7
 General quality (25%): 9
 Total points (out of 100): 73

Comments for the Authors

The proposal deals with a topic, of reliability and efficient O&M of PV systems, which is of a high priority at a EU level and it is also in-line with the ERIGRID2.0 research area. The description of the proposal is very informative and of a good quality. The proposal tries to use datasets from a simulated behavior of PV modules representing aging and failure mechanisms, in order to train failure detection and diagnosis (FDD) algorithms. For procedures simulating aging there is always a concern about how close to real conditions this simulation is. It would be interesting to investigate the validity and comparison of the patterns found in the datasets of this simulated operation with datasets from the field operation PV systems, in this or in a future work. The proposal will improve the know-how and capacities of two labs of the ERIGRID2.0, through the involvement of two important partners and the mutual benefits from synergies.

Review 3

=====

Evaluation of the Proposal

Merit (25%): 9
 Improve know-how (25%): 10
 Compliance (25%): 10
 General quality (25%): 9
 Total points (out of 100): 95

Comments for the Authors

It is very good project. I would recommend it.

In case of questions do not hesitate to contact us at access@erigrd2.eu.

Best regards,

Your ERIGrid 2.0 Team

—

ERIGrid 2.0

<https://www.conftool.net/erigrd2/>

Consortium

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